

Quantitative Relationship of Diamagnetic Susceptibility with Molecular Connectivity and van der Waals Volume in Alcohols

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A quantitative analysis is made on the relationship of diamagnetic susceptibility of alcohols with Kier's molecular connectivity (${}^1X^V$) and van der Waals volume (V_w). The regression analysis reveals a significant linear correlation of diamagnetic susceptibility with ${}^1X^V$ and V_w .

The molecular connectivity index 1X_v signified the degree of branching, connectivity in a molecule. Kier *et al.*¹ have shown that this index can be correlated with several physicochemical and biological properties of the molecules. The molecular connectivity has several versions. The simplest as well as extended versions in it all are calculated from a hydrogen suppressed graph of the molecule. The simplest version designated as first order valence connectivity, 1X_v is given by equation (1),

$${}^1X^v = \sum (\delta_i^v \delta_j^v)^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

Here the sum is the overall connections of edges in such a graph and δ_i^v and δ_j^v are numbers assigned to each atom reflecting the number of atoms adjacent or connected to atoms i and j , which are formally bonded. The atom connectivity term δ_i^v is defined as

$$\delta_i^v = \frac{Z_i^v - h_i}{Z - Z_i^v - 1} \quad (2)$$

where, Z_i^v is the number of valence electrons or atom i , Z the atomic number of atom i and h_i the number of hydrogen atoms attached to atom i .

Another parameter accounting for the size of a molecule, the van der Waals volume (V_w) has also been used for the correlation with diamagnetic susceptibility. The atoms are assumed to be spherical while calculating the V_w as suggested by Bondi². The necessary corrections for the overlap of atomic orbitals, and for the branching in hydrocarbon chain are also incorporated³.

It is generally known that the diamagnetic susceptibility for many organic compounds may be predicted theoretically by considering it more or less additive⁴. The molar susceptibility for various homologous series of organic compounds can be determined by additive methods considering different functional groups and connections. Various semi-empirical theories have been given for the calculation of diamagnetic susceptibilities of organic compounds. The best theory was proposed by Pascal⁵. The molar susceptibility of an organic compound is represented as

$$X_m = \sum n_A X_A \quad (3)$$

where the summation is to be performed over all atomic species in the molecule, n_A is the number of atom A present, and X is the susceptibility contribution of atom A to the total susceptibility. This theory has been remarkably successful, specially in comparison to other semi-empirical theories. In spite of all positive features, it does not count the effects of variation in bonding. The susceptibility of a doubly bound oxygen atom, as in an aldehyde, is quite different from contribution of a singly bound oxygen, as in an alcohol. So Pascal accounted for these variations by replacing equation (3) by

$$X_m = n_A X_A + \sum \alpha \quad (4)$$

where α is a correction which depends on the nature of the bonds between the atoms. The Pascal theory could not account for the differences in susceptibility between different isomers, although these are small. We established earlier⁶, a quantitative relationship of diamagnetic susceptibility with molecular connectivity in hydrocarbons, and found a higher degree of relationship. Attempt has now been made to correlate diamagnetic susceptibility with molecular connectivity and van der Waals volume in alcohol series; because both parameters account for the degree of branching, connections and size of the molecules, as diamagnetic susceptibility.

Results and Discussion

The molecular connectivity 1X_v and van der Waals volume are calculated for some alcohols as described in literature. These are listed in Table 1. The diamagnetic susceptibility values are taken from literature⁷⁻¹⁵.

The level of significance of this linear correlation diamagnetic susceptibility X_m with molecular connectivity (${}^1X^V$) and van der Waals volume (V_w) are shown by equations (5) and (6),

$$X_m = 22.743 {}^1X^V (\pm 0.640) + 13.697 \quad (5)$$

$$N = 23, r = 0.991, s = 3.633, F(1, 21) = 1259.099$$

$$X_m = 76.733 V_w (\pm 1.974) - 2.203 \quad (6)$$

$$N = 23, r = 0.993, s = 3.322, F(1, 21) = 1510.433$$

TABLE I—DIAMAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY, X_V AND V_w OF SOME ALCOHOLS

Compd.	1X_V	V_w	X_m			Ref.		
			Exp.	Calcd. (eq. 5)	Calcd. (eq. 6)			
Methanol	0.447	0.330	21.15	23.86	23.11	7		
			21.40*			8		
			21.60			9		
Ethanol	1.023	0.481	33.05	3.96	34.70	7		
			33.60*			8		
			33.55			9		
n-Propanol	1.523	0.633	44.44	45.3	46.36	7		
			45.20*			8		
			45.176			9		
Isopropanol	1.412	0.583	47.22	45.81	45.53	10		
			45.68			7		
			45.79*			9		
n-Butanol	2.023	0.784	47.63	56.70	57.95	10		
			56.15			7		
			55.90			8		
s-Butanol	1.950	0.784	56.53*	58.04	57.95	9		
			58.58			10		
			57.30			7		
Isobutanol	1.878	0.734	57.68*	56.43	57.11	9		
			57.6			11		
			57.9			11		
t-Butanol	1.723	0.684	57.21	57.88	50.28	7		
n-Pentanol	2.523	0.936	57.70*	71.08	69.61	7		
s-Pentanol	2.450	0.936	59.89	93.02	92.86	12		
Isopentanol	2.379	0.886	69.1			69.42	69.61	11
			69.8*			7		
n-Hexanol	3.023	1.087	68.96	67.80	66.78	7		
4-Methyl-2-pentanol	2.806	1.037	79.20	80.45	80.20	8		
			80.4*	82.51	80.36	11		
4-Heptanol	3.488	1.239	82.1	93.02	92.86	11		
			91.5*			11		
2,6-Dimethyl-4-heptanol	4.200	1.442	93.5	119.22	118.44	11		
			116.9*			11		
Octanol	4.023	1.390	117.2	102.19	104.45	11		
Dodecanol	6.207	1.971	102.65	102.77	149.03	14		
Glycol	1.132	0.555	147.10	150.77	149.03	14		
1,4-Butanediol	2.132	0.858	38.80	39.44	38.33	14		
2,4-Pentanediol	2.632	1.010	61.50	62.18	63.63	15		
			70.4	70.55	74.29	11		
Hexamethylene-glycol	3.132	1.161	74.4	84.93	86.88	11		
			84.3			8		

Glycerol	1.648	0.799	57.06	57.17	59.10	8
Erythritol	2.298	1.007	73.80	75.96	75.06	8

*The experimental values (if more than one) are the ones that are used for regression analysis. The resulting theoretical and experimental values of diamagnetic susceptibilities are expressed in terms of 10^{-6} cgs units or $4\pi \times 10^{-9}$ SI units.

In regression analysis, the statistical parameters (n = the number of data points, r = the correlation coefficient, s = the standard deviation and F = the ratio between the variance of calculated and observed data) exhibit very high level of significance of the correlation. The diamagnetic susceptibility values calculated from equations (5) and (6) are found to be very close to the experimental values. These equations can be used to predict the diamagnetic susceptibility of any alcohol by simply calculating 1X_V or V_w .

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